

Methods of Calculating Plastics under Load and Environmental Effects

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ABSTRACT

When applying plastics for bearing constructions in civil engineering one has to consider time, loading and environmental effects in a different way than when using traditional materials, as the time-dependent stress-strain behavior influences also the effective strength.

With the here proposed new dimensioning method for glass fibre reinforced plastics (mat-laminates) it is possible to calculate all influences depending on time with simple formulas, where all necessary factors can be assembled in tables, see (1,2). The advantage consists in the possibility to separate the different effects and to permit an optimal and economic use of the material.

INTRODUCTION

Long-term constant loadings on plastic constructions cause strains with non-neglectable elastic and creep deformations and decreases of the effective strength. Variable environmental effects (temperature, ageing) have to be superimposed.

As creep rate curves of plastics show, see Figure 1, that there is a strong connection between the extent of creep deformation and decrease of strength during the required lifetime (generally a time of $1-2 \cdot 10^5$ h, i.e. 12-25 years), an economic method of calculating bearing plastic constructions can only be formulated on this basis.

Fig. 1: Influence of long-term loading on time-dependent creep deformation $\epsilon(t)$ and long-term strength $\beta(t)$ (t_L = lifetime for $\sigma = \sigma_2 = \text{const}$)

TIME-DEPENDENT STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR AND STRENGTH

Time-dependent Deformation Modulus

The following equations show the formulation of the time-dependent deformation modulus $E_c(t)$ based on visco-elastic behavior of plastics (constant stress σ and constant temperature ϑ).

$$E_c(t) = E_0 / (1 + \varphi(t)) \quad (1)$$

$$\varphi(t) = \epsilon_c(t) / \epsilon_0 \quad (2)$$

where E_0 short-term modulus of elasticity
 $\epsilon(t)$ time-dependent deformation
 ϵ_0 elastic deformation
 $\epsilon_c(t)$ creep deformation

For a projected lifetime t_L eq. (1) can be transformed by:

$$\varphi(t_L) = \varphi_L \quad (3)$$

$$\varphi(t) = n_E(t) \cdot \varphi_L \quad (4)$$

$$E_c(t) = E_{n\varphi} = E_0 / (1 + n_E(t) \cdot \varphi_L) \quad (5)$$

The term $E_{n\varphi}$, see (1), describes just like $E_c(t)$ a time-dependent modulus of deformation, which includes by the value of the time-factor $n_E(t)$ the influence of time within $0 \leq t \leq t_L$.

Time-dependent Strength

According to eq. (5) the time-dependent strength $\beta(t)$ at constant temperature ϑ can be described by:

$$\beta(t) = \beta_0 / (1 + n_\sigma(t) \cdot \Delta \beta / \beta_L) \quad (6)$$

where β_0 short-term strength
 β_L long-term strength
 $\Delta\beta = \beta_0 - \beta_L$ strength decrease during the projected lifetime t_L
 $n_0(t)$ time-factor

As the calculation of the real stress-strain behavior of bearing plastics under the influence of real loading in most cases would be too difficult for dimensioning, simple methods had to be developed.

DIMENSIONING METHODS OF LOAD-BEARING PLASTICS

Dimensioning Method with Diminution Factors

In case of dimensioning load-bearing plastics (GRP mat-laminates), in Germany mostly a method based on diminution factors is used, which correlates the influence of long-term loading, temperature, ageing and production on short-term and long-term behavior by diminution factors A_i . They are formulated by analyses and extrapolations of results of tests and by estimating, see (2), e.g.

$$\sigma_a = \beta_0 / (\gamma \cdot A_1 \cdot A_2 \cdot A_3 \cdot A_4) \quad (7)$$

where γ factor of safety as for usual constructions
 A_i factors regarding long-term loading, ageing, temperature and production

But as the effects of real loading, e.g. of wind and snow, see Figure 2, are only estimated but not calculated and as the mutual influence of the various parameters is not specified, see (1), it has been tried to find out a new and more complete method.

Fig. 2: Frequency of wind loads and course of snow loads

New Dimensioning Method

This new dimensioning method, see (3,4), based on the real material behavior, takes into account all load-, temperature- and ageing-influences in a more appropriate way.

Influence of Real Loading.

As real loading is not constant except for the dead weight, creep deformation and strength decrease have to be calculated dependent on the real course of loading. In case of the dimensioning being based on constant maximum loads only, uneconomical calculations would be the result. Therefore it is recommended to formulate equivalent loads (creep loads, see (1)), which show just like the actual loads the same creep deformation as well as the same strength decrease within the projected lifetime.

In accordance with eq. (5) and (6) the influence of real loading on deformation and strength can be described by loading-factors $n_E(\sigma)$ and $n_L(\sigma)$, see (4), with short-term loading $n_{E,\sigma}(\sigma) = 0$ and long-term constant loading $n_{E,\sigma}(\sigma) = 1$.

Temperature and Ageing

In addition to the strain caused by variable loads, the influences of variable temperature courses ϑ , see Figure 3, and ageing A, see Figure 4 and 5, are effective for outdoor constructions.

Fig. 3: Course of air temperature

Fig. 4: Sunshine radiation (5)

Fig. 5: Sunshine radiation (6)

Fig. 6: Duration of sunshine

For dimensioning the long-term values φ_L and $\Delta B/B_L$ are completed by temperature- and ageing-factors α_{LE} and $\alpha_{L\sigma}$ (long-term temperature course and ageing under long-term loading $n_{E,\sigma} = 1$) and the short-term values E_0 and β_0 by α_{0E} and $\alpha_{0\sigma}$ (maximum temperature and ageing under short-term loading, $n_{E,\sigma} = 0$), see Figure 7, (4,7).

$$\alpha_{0E}(\vartheta, A) = \frac{E_0(\vartheta, A)}{E_0(\vartheta_0, A_0)} \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_{LE}(\vartheta, A) = \frac{\varphi_L(\vartheta, A)}{\varphi_L(\vartheta_0, A_0)} \quad (9)$$

$$\alpha_{0\sigma}(\vartheta, A) = \frac{\beta_0(\vartheta, A)}{\beta_0(\vartheta_0, A_0)} \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha_{L\sigma}(\vartheta, A) = \frac{\Delta B(\vartheta, A)/B_L(\vartheta, A)}{\Delta B(\vartheta_0, A_0)/B_L(\vartheta_0, A_0)} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 7: Definition of temperature- and ageing-factors

The Final Dimensioning Formulas. The Final Dimensioning Formulas taking into account all influences mentioned before can be formulated by long-term modulus of deformation

$$E_{n\varphi SA} = \frac{\alpha_{0E} \cdot E_0}{1 + n_E(\sigma) \cdot \varphi_L \cdot \alpha_{LE}} \quad (12)$$

and admissible stress based on effective strength

$$\sigma_a = \frac{\beta}{\gamma} = \frac{\alpha_{o\sigma} \cdot \beta_o}{\gamma(1+n_{E,\sigma}(\sigma)) \cdot \frac{\Delta\beta}{\beta_L} \cdot \alpha_{L\sigma}} \quad (13)$$

where α_{oE} , $\alpha_{o\sigma}$ short-term temperature- and ageing-factors
 ($n_{E,\sigma} = 0$)
 α_{LE} , $\alpha_{L\sigma}$ long-term temperature- and ageing-factors
 ($n_{E,\sigma} = 1$)
 $n_{E,\sigma}(\sigma)$ loading-factors

Using 5 o/o-values for E_o , φ_L , β_o and β_L an additional consideration of production influence can be neglected.

SUMMARY

By this new method, dimensioning of plastic constructions is possible according to the usual static calculation rules, considering all time-depending influences and permitting an optimal and economic use of the material.

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